

**FACTORS ENSURING THE COMPETITIVENESS OF SMALL
BUSINESS SUBJECTS****Xodjimirzayeva Sayyora Muxiddinovna¹****Ahmedov Oybek Turgunpulatovich²**¹⁻²Namangan Engineering Construction Institute Namangan,
Republic of Uzbekistan<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7238577>

The ability and capacity of small business entities to provide world-class services and products in the supply chain reduces the cost of production and dependence on imported materials of large enterprises. As businesses seek to reduce cost and cycle time in an ever-competitive global economy, large enterprises are forced to support the development of local suppliers to grow with their businesses, meaning they are willing to provide significant human and financial resources to strengthen the competitiveness of their small business partners. Research shows that best practices include:

- facilitating access of small business entities to innovation centers of large enterprises;
- assignment of employees of large enterprises, including engineers and management consultants, to small business entities; and
- Phased upgrade of production capacity, from operations and plant location to design capability, flexible manufacturing, ISO certifications and R&D capabilities. Most importantly, large enterprises should cooperate with the government to improve the level of skills.

Offering the most cost-effective education while bridging the gap between the skills taught in public institutions and the skills required on the job. Such tailored training is an important enabler for small businesses to embrace technology and engage in continuous innovation.

The findings suggest that participation in large enterprises contributes more to competitive skills than basic education, especially when large enterprises provide on-the-job training and cooperative training. State-of-the-art equipment, computer technology and software allow learning to use the same industry-standard tools found in modern businesses. One of the most innovative programs that establish direct connections between large enterprises and small business entities is the global supplier program. This program is the result of a joint effort between the state government and the industry and consists of two initiatives: basic training in essential skills and linkages with large enterprises.

In the first part, manufacturing and material suppliers are trained in the essential skills and competencies to adopt and use new technologies. In the

second part of the program, large enterprises adopt local small businesses and "capture" them to improve their leadership skills and technologies. This initiative requires an investment of time and commitment by large enterprises and small business entities. The success of this coaching will be evident when the suppliers achieve the level of competence to become global players themselves. An important part of the linkage program is the periodic evaluation and review of small business entities by large enterprises.

Research shows that sharing knowledge about market trends with small business entities as well as large enterprises in the upcoming seminar is critical to connecting with their partners. Also, large enterprises help small businesses develop other business opportunities in addition to communication software. This proposal for the development of competitive small business entities will affect the creation of new jobs, income generation, exports and internationalization of enterprises, and will provide basic training and logistics infrastructure.

It is clear from this that it is appropriate to establish a "Business Center" in the regions, and it is envisaged that the center will develop special programs to be ready to cooperate with small business entities and establish communication relations with large enterprises and guide them in establishing strong cooperative relations. Ultimately, the country will benefit from the globalization of small businesses. In general, best practices demonstrated by case studies are based on the principle of subsidiarity. Experience shows that the conditions for success by increasing the competitiveness of small business entities are as follows:

- governments should act as a catalyst by providing logistics and educational infrastructure, continuous improvement, particularly by developing engineering and management skills. A business-friendly environment must be based on meaningful and continuous public-private dialogue so that the public sector understands the business needs of large enterprises and small business entities. Investment policies and incentives should be targeted at large enterprises that are eager to grow and willing to enter into supplier development programs.
- public and private sectors, as well as academia, should work together to create "meso" institutions such as centers of excellence to facilitate technology transfer and achieve continuous innovation potential.
- connects businesses working with small businesses for technological and management upgrades by having large businesses act as change agents or host small businesses and mentor them on continuous improvement. In this regard,

large enterprises have a great potential to facilitate the universal use of information technology and the possibility of adopting new methods of commercial operations, including e-commerce.

Studies show that the main reason for the weak linkages of large enterprises with local small business entities is the absence of effective small business entities that can capture new business opportunities associated with foreign direct investment. Barriers to entry for cooperation with large enterprises differ significantly accordingly

1. Type of Partnership Intended: Requirements for suppliers are not the same as requirements for distributors or joint venture partners.
2. Reasons why large enterprises seek to cooperate with local small business entities, to acquire new technologies, use the advantages of specialization, reduce labor costs, etc.
3. Characteristics of industrial activity, technological complexity, capital and scale requirements. As for small businesses as suppliers to large enterprises, barriers to entry can be relatively low, especially in technologically simple and labor-intensive activities such as assembling clothes, shoes, and toys. In this activity, low wages and labor standards, externalizing environmental costs or willingness to accept unstable demand conditions may be sufficient to accept as a supplier to large enterprises. Nevertheless, compliance with quality standards is becoming more and more important, especially when production is associated with a company or brand name.

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